

Collaborative Authorship in Scholarly Indian Publications in Biochemistry

A Study based on the *Web of Science*

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Abstract

Using Web of Science as the source of data, the authors investigate the characteristics of research contributions in biochemistry emanated from India during 2004-2013. A total of 25132 items have been identified as produced during a span of 10 years, and their annual growth rate is estimated as 12.5% with the exception of the year 2013. Almost 97.5% of the contributions are of collaborative authorship, with number of authors in the range of 2 to 253. Groups comprising 2 to 4 scientists are found responsible for 62.8% of the contributions. Three member groups have authored the maximum share of 22.83% papers. Degree of collaboration of biochemists as reflected in Indian contributions is in the range of 0.97 to 0.98. Mean of Co-Authorship Index (CAI) estimated for three blocks, namely single-authored, two author and >2 author contributions are found to be 104.4, 102.7 and 99.2 respectively. A consistent increase in CAI of more than 2 author contributions is observed since 2010.

Keywords: Authorship Pattern ; Biochemistry Literature – India ; Co-authorship Index ; Degree of Collaboration ; Scholarly Literature – Biochemistry ; Web of Science

1. Introduction

Biochemistry, in broad terms, is the study of the chemical composition of the living organisms and the biochemical processes that underlie life activities during their growth and maintenance. It is one of the academic disciplines in life science that studies the structure, function, metabolism and the mechanism of the components in the cells: such as proteins, carbohydrates, lipids, nucleic acids and vitamins up to the molecular level. There has been a lot of

research on the subject of biochemistry and after due deliberations, their definitions have been set as to what is biochemistry. The subject of biochemistry occupies a central position in modern biological research and has been developed rapidly in the early 20th century. In classification schemes, it is placed between science and medicine. As the soul of life sciences, biochemistry has a versatile scope in the field of agriculture, pharmaceutical, nutritional, and medical sciences. Chemical compounds and

processes that occur in, or are caused by living organisms come under the purview of biochemistry. It encompasses all aspects of biology, from molecules to cells, to organisms, to medicine, and toxicology.

Until the 1960s, the study of biochemistry was centered on primary metabolism of small molecules, in particular on how energy is produced, stored and the metabolism of the basic building blocks like amino acids, carbohydrates, lipid compounds and nucleotides. However, with the import of physical and genetic techniques that enable the determination of DNA and the discovery of the genetic code, the field of biochemistry grew enormously. Biochemists find their position in different departments according to their diverse interests, including molecular biology, animal biology and plant biology.

Authorship and collaborative research are the important facets of informetrics / scientometric studies. Collaboration and team work are among the most important necessities of scientific and technological work today. In recent period, there is a trend towards collaboration in research in almost all pure and applied sciences. It has been found that a large number of collaborative studies have been reported in the field of science and technology than in social sciences and humanities. It is generally seen that patterns and magnitude of collaboration differ with discipline and period covered in the study.

2. Previous Studies

A number of authorship related studies have already been carried out by eminent scientists and research scholars in various subject fields. Lotka (1926) was the first to make a systematic study of author productivity and he formulated the well known inverse square law. Derek J De Solla Price (1963) was the first to study the authorship pattern and based on his survey of Chemical Abstracts, observed that there is a steady trend towards multi-authorship and if it continues at the then observed rate, he even postulated that, the single author papers will be extinct by 1980's. A decrease in the number of papers published by the single authors is clearly evident in the recent research which goes side by side with the above postulate.

Maheswarappa & Mathias (1987) made a study of the authorship collaboration in various disciplines of physical sciences. Begum & Rajendra (1990) and Vimala & Pulla Reddy (1996) investigated the collaborative research in zoology. The correlation between multiple authorship and citedness in the field of immunology was examined by Arora & Pawan (1995). The extent of multiple authorship in different disciplines such as mathematics, physics, mechanical engineering, philosophy and political science have been studied by Bandyopadhyay (2001; 2004). The study is based on the references appended to 92 doctoral theses submitted to the University of Burdwan, India from 1981 to 1990. Farhat (2002), Krishna & Kumar (2004), and Kumbar et al. (2004) have studied the authorship trend and collaboration in the field of agriculture science.

Analysing the citations to journal articles and books collected from the doctoral dissertations of the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, Sudhier (2007) estimated that the average degree of collaboration of authorship in journals and in books are 0.80 and 0.44 respectively for physics literature. Zafrunnisha & Pulla Reddy (2009) studied the authorship pattern and degree of collaboration in psychology by sampling 141 Ph.D. theses of universities. Predominance of multi-authored papers over single authored was observed in the study. The joint paper by Kumbar & Girish Kumar (2011) is about authorship trend and collaborative research in genetics and plant breeding. The authorship pattern and collaboration in Indian chemistry literature were investigated by Pradhan et al. (2011). A similar study in veterinary science is reported by Arya & Sharma (2011).

Other studies on authorship trend and collaboration include the one on marine sciences by Elango & Rajendran (2012), on network security by Amsaveni & Vasanthi (2013), on chemical sciences by Goyal et al (2013), on information technology by Khaparde & Pawar (2013), on horticulture by Tunga (2014), on Indian literature on intellectual property rights by Velmurugan & Radhakrishnan (2015) on space craft technology by Iqbalahmed & Ashalatha (2015), and on LIS by Shivcharan & Sandeep Kumar (2015). Collaborative authorship was found to

predominate in all these studies and they admitted the fact that the research in the field is collaborative in all respect. Amsaveni & Manjula (2014) made an attempt to evolve statistical models to the collaborative publications in the field of bio-informatics for the period 1999-2013. Using the *Web of Science* database as the source of data, Senthilkumar & Muthukrishnan (2016) studied the authorship pattern and collaborative research of oncology research in India and Manya & Sudhier (2017) in the field of Bio-informatics. The present study makes a detailed investigation into the pattern of authorship and research collaboration in the field of biochemistry in India during the period 2004-2013.

3. Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to find out the extent of collaboration and co-authorship in the Indian biochemistry research. The following are the specific objectives with which the study was carried out.

- i. To estimate the number of research contributions emanating from India in an year and calculate the annual growth rate.
- ii. To examine the the nature of authorship of the research publications in biochemistry originating from India and to identify the most productive authors.
- iii. To know about the extent of single and multi-authored publications in Indian biochemistry literature.
- iv. To estimate the degree of collaboration between scientists as reflected in the research papers.
- v. To measure the co-authorship index in biochemistry research output from India.

4. Methodology

The data for the present study were accessed from *Web of Science* formerly published by the Thomson Reuters and now by Clarivate Analytics. The basic data relating to biochemistry publications from India for a period of 10 years (2004-13) are collected using general search option of *Web of Science*. In the address field of the general search option, the term India was used. Additionally, in the publication

year field every year from 2004 to 2013 was searched. In the key word area, the following key words were given: 'biochemistry in India, metabolism in India, proteins biochemistry in India, enzymes in India, and genetics in India'. The total population consists of 25,132 research contributions covered in the database from January 2004 to December 2013. All the searched results were first saved in text files and then imported into Microsoft Excel for analysis. The data were sorted to prepare tables and figures and analysed scientometrically using the SPSS software.

Degree of Collaboration

The degree of collaboration of authors, was calculated using the mathematical formula proposed by Subramaniam (1983). He defined, the degree of collaboration of an author as the ratio of the number of multi-authored papers that he / she has contributed to the total number of papers published by him / her during a given period of time. The degree of collaboration among authors is defined mathematically as :

$$C = Nm / (Nm + Ns)$$

Where, C = Degree of collaboration

Nm = number of multi-authored papers by the author during a given period, and

Ns = number of single-authored papers by the author during the same period.

This formula can very well be applied to estimate the degree of collaboration in a subject field.

Co-Authorship Index

Garg and Padhi (2001) proposed a formula to find out how the pattern of co-authors has changed, and this formula was used for finding the Co-Authorship Index (CAI). The formula suggested is:

$$CAI = \{(N_{ij} / N_{io}) / (N_{oj} / N_{oo})\} 100$$

Where N_{ij} = number of papers having j authors in block i
 N_{io} = Total output of block i

N_{oj} = Number of papers having j authors for all blocks.

N_{oo} = Total number of papers for all authors in all blocks

$$J = 1, 2, 3 \dots n$$

5. Data Analysis

5.1 Year-wise distribution of research output

During 2004-2013, Indian scientists published 25,132 articles on the domain of biochemistry and its sub-disciplines. Annual average comes to 2513. Year-wise break up of the data shown in table 1 indicates that there is a steady increase during 2004 to 2012, with highest number of 3491 publications (13.89%) in

the year 2012. It is evident that biochemistry research in the country is growing steadily (fig. 1). A slight fall in the number is observed in 2013. With the exception of this, the average annual growth rate is 12.5%.

5.2 Most productive authors

The most productive authors were identified based on first author count. The table 2 gives a ranked list of prolific authors who have contributed more than 10 papers during the period of study.

Table 1 : Year-wise distribution of research output

Sl. No.	Year	Count	Percentage
1	2004	1369	5.45
2	2005	1621	6.45
3	2006	1859	7.4
4	2007	2181	8.68
5	2008	2489	9.90
6	2009	2658	10.58
7	2010	2880	11.46
8	2011	3252	12.94
9	2012	3491	13.89
10	2013	3332	13.26
	Total	25,132	100.00

Figure 1 : Trend in the growth of Indian Biochemistry research

Table 2 : Most productive authors

Sl. No.	Author	Count	Percentage	Rank
1	Abdul Jaleel, C.	58	0.23	1
2	Pari, L	37	0.15	2
3	Kumar, S	26	0.10	3
4	Tripathi, G	24	0.10	4
5	Manoj Kumar	23	0.09	5
6	Puneet Kumar	22	0.09	6
7	Sharma, S	21	0.08	7
8	Anil Kumar	20	0.08	8
9	Gupta, S	18	0.07	9
10	Kamal, A	18	0.07	9
11	Kumar, R	18	0.07	9
12	Das, U. K.	17	0.07	10
13	Kumar, A	17	0.07	10
14	Sharma, A	16	0.06	11
15	Srivastava, S	16	0.06	11
16	Batra, V	15	0.06	12
17	Kaur, Gurpreet	15	0.06	12
18	Srivastava, Sudhakar	15	0.06	12
19	Anandakumar, P.	14	0.06	13
20	Balakumar, Pitchai	14	0.06	13

C. Abdul Jaleel, the most productive author, has contributed 58 papers (0.23%) during the period of study and he is followed by L. Pari with 37 (0.15%) papers and S. Kumar with 26 (0.10%) papers.

5.3 Authorship Pattern

Papers in biochemistry are found to be authored by 1 to 253 authors in the byline. Among the Indian research papers in biochemistry published during 2004 to 2013, only 2.5% are single author papers (table 3 and fig. 2). About 76.3% papers have been authored collaboratively by two to five authors each. Three author papers which account for about 23% of the total, are seen to be the modal group in the distribution. Except for the year 2013, a regular increase is observed for papers with joint authorship.

Citation studies indicate that multi-authored papers get more citations than single author papers. The authorship pattern, one of the prime aspects of citation analysis, mainly deals with the kind of authors, nature and degree of collaboration and collaborative trend of authors. As biochemistry as a subject is multi-disciplinary in nature and research is a laboratory-intensive activity, it is natural to find multi-authorship pattern in the domain.

5.4 Degree of Collaboration

Collaboration is said to have taken place when two or more investigators work together on a project and contribute resources and effort, both intellectual and physical. Collaborative research is very common in the field of science and technology today. Degree

Table 3 : Frequency distribution of papers in biochemistry by number of authors

No. of authors	Year of publication										Total	%
	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013		
1	44	40	50	75	80	77	80	73	58	54	631	2.51
2	340	358	427	501	539	540	596	614	641	589	5145	20.47
3	356	413	446	523	613	614	614	733	733	693	5738	22.83
4	286	321	342	428	508	539	553	605	689	629	4900	19.5
5	156	228	242	279	302	338	408	483	481	488	3405	13.55
6	91	97	171	149	177	229	222	300	346	325	2107	8.38
7	52	59	90	106	107	115	145	164	201	207	1246	4.96
8	18	47	44	57	65	72	101	91	116	126	737	2.93
9	13	31	19	22	34	50	57	56	80	85	447	1.78
10+	13	27	28	41	64	85	104	133	145	136	775	3.08
Total	1369	1621	1859	2181	2489	2659	2880	3252	3490	3332	25132	100

Figure 2 : Authorship pattern in biochemistry

of collaboration can be measured based on multi-authored papers. It is the ratio of the number of collaborative research papers during a given period of time to the total number of research papers during the same period. In other words, it is the number of collaborative papers divided by the total number of papers.

The formula that Subramanyam (1983) has devised to calculate the degree of collaboration of an author, is as the ratio of the joint-authored contributions of the author and the total number (both single authored and joint-authored) of contributions by him or her. Assuming that the same formula would apply to the degree of collaboration in a subject field, the degree of collaboration in biochemistry research in India in each year during 2004-2013 was calculated and tabulated in table 5. The values are found to be

in the range of 0.97 to 0.98, indicating a very high degree of collaboration and remains almost stable during the ten year period of study.

5.5 Co-Authorship Index

As already pointed out, Co-Authorship Index (CAI) was calculated using the formula proposed by Garg and Padhi (2003). The CAI = 100 implies that co-authorship in the particular block corresponds to overall average of the population. CAI > 100 indicates that co-authorship in the block is higher than the overall average and CAI < 100 denotes a lower than average. To analyse the CAI, the total research contributions covered in the study were divided into three blocks, namely 'single author papers', two author papers' and 'more than two author papers'. Year-wise CAI were calculated for each block (table 6.)

Table 5 : Degree of Collaboration

Sl. No.	Year	Single authors	Multi-authors	Total	Degree of collaboration
1	2004	44	1325	1369	0.97
2	2005	40	1581	1621	0.98
3	2006	50	1809	1859	0.97
4	2007	75	2106	2181	0.97
5	2008	80	2409	2489	0.97
6	2009	77	2581	2658	0.97
7	2010	80	2800	2880	0.97
8	2011	73	3179	3252	0.98
9	2012	58	3432	3490	0.98
10	2013	54	3279	3333	0.98

Table 6 : Co-Authorship Index

Year	'Single author' papers		'Two author' papers		'>2 author' papers		Total no.
	No.	CAI	No.	CAI	No.	CAI	
2004	44	128	340	121	985	93	1369
2005	40	98	358	108	1223	98	1621
2006	50	107	427	112	1382	97	1859
2007	75	137	501	112	1606	96	2182
2008	80	128	539	106	1870	98	2489
2009	77	115	540	99	2041	100	2658
2010	80	111	596	101	2204	99	2880
2011	73	89	614	92	2565	102	3252
2012	58	66	641	90	2791	104	3491
2013	54	65	589	86	2689	105	3332
Total	631		5145		19355		25132

For the first block, the CAI is in the range of 65 to 137, with an average of 104.4. For papers with two joint authors, the CAI is in the range of 86 to 121. The mean of CAI comes to 102.7. In the case of contributions with more than two authors the CAI is seen to be in the range of 93 to 105, with a mean of 99.2. The third block is seen to have CAI slightly less than the overall average. The regular increase in the CAI of the third block since 2010 shows the increasing tendency in collaborative research in the field of biochemistry in India. As already indicated, it is a common observation that co-authored papers tend to be cited more frequently and biochemistry research in India is no exception to this. Moreover, papers with foreign co-authors draw more citations than those having only internal collaborations within the country. It is observed from the analysis that generally the value of CAI is increasing during the period of study. This implies that Indian research in biochemistry field is mainly characterized by collaborative work and not by solo research.

6. Summary of Findings

The important findings of the study are:

- The *Web of Science* recorded a total of 25132 research publications in biochemistry as emanated from India during the period 2004-2013. The average annual output is 2513, and annual growth rate up to 2012 is estimated as 12.5%. The highest number of publications (3491) came out in 2012. The number of publications in 2013 is less than that in the previous year by 4.6%.
- India's share in the world biochemistry output is 3.6 % during the period 2004 – 2013.
- Based on first author count, C. Abdual Jaleel is identified as the most productive author with 58 papers during 10 year period of study, followed by L. Pari with 37 papers and S. Kumar with 26 papers.
- About 97.5% of publications are contributed by multi-authors, the number of authors ranging from 2 to 253 . Only 2.5% (631) are single author contributions.
- Joint groups of two scientists each account for 5145 papers (20.5%) and of three scientists each

for 5738 papers (22.83%). The two groups together are responsible for 43.33% of the total output from India. Further, 76.3% of the papers are of joint authorship comprising two to five members each.

- The degree of collaboration of authors of research publications in biochemistry emanating from India is estimated as in the range of 0.97 to 0.98.
- It is observed from the analysis that the values of CAI show generally an increasing trend annually and vary from 93 to 105 during the period 2004 – 2013.

7. Conclusion

The study of collaborative authorship in biochemistry research publications from India has revealed many interesting features of scholarly literature as well as Indian research in the subject field. The present study is concentrated on the number of authors alone, of the biochemistry research contributions covered in the WoS database. The extensive collaboration as revealed in the quantitative parameters such as percentage of multi-authored papers, degree of collaboration and co-authorship index is indicative of the high extent of team research in biochemistry in India. The findings substantiate the scope for further studies, particularly about the institutional / departmental affiliation of scientists in the collaborating groups, the level of international collaboration and the collaborative authorship vis-a-vis citations received in journals with high impact factor.

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